

Genetic evaluation & utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Sources of disease and insect resistance in selections of improved plant type

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Incorporation of disease and insect resistance into improved germ plasm is a major objective of the IRRI GEU program. The several donor parents that have been used as sources of resistance to each major disease and insect have poor plant type (tall with weak stems and droopy leaves). They were crossed with rices of improved plant type such as TN1, IR8, IR262-43-8, and IR24. Semidwarf lines with good grain quality and resistance to specific diseases or insects were selected and evaluated for several seasons and intercrossed to develop lines with multiple resistance. The combining ability of each line was determined from the performance of hybrid progeny that resulted from a series of crosses involving the line. Only the progeny with good combining ability were saved.

We used several sources of resistance to each pest and disease except grassy stunt virus, for which *Oryza nivara* is the only source of resistance. For blast, such donor parents as Gam Pai 15, H 105, Sigadis, Nahng Mon S-4, Dawn, Zenith, Kam Bau Ngan, and Tetep were used. For bacterial blight we used Zenith, Malagkit Sungsong, TKM6, Sigadis, Wase Aikoku 3, BJ1, and DZ 192. For tungro, we used Gam Pai 15, TKM6, Peta, Pankhari 203, Malagkit Sungsong, HR21, C013, and Ptb 18.

Five genes for resistance to green leafhopper are known; three of them have been incorporated into rices of the semidwarf plant type. Of the four known genes for resistance to brown planthopper, two have been transferred into selections of improved plant type. Genes for resistance to different diseases and insects have been studied in various combinations.

A list of 110 selections, with data on their parents, their accession numbers, and their reactions to blast, bacterial blight, tungro, and grassy stunt diseases, and to the green leafhopper and brown

planthopper, is available at the IRRI plant breeding department. The lines may be used instead of tall donor parents in hybridization programs as sources of disease and insect resistance. Scientists in national programs may obtain lists of these 110 elite lines, and their seeds, from the IRRI Plant Breeding Department.

Impact of semidwarfs on the area planted, production, and yield of rice in the Punjab of India

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The landlocked state of the Punjab lies within latitudes 29°30' to 39°30' north and longitudes 73°55' to 76°50' east in the Indo-Gangetic Plain of northern India. One of the smaller states of India, it has an area of 50,376 sq km which is alluvial in nature. It has two main crop-sowing seasons, the rabi (October – November) and kharif (June – July). The important rabi crops are wheat, gram, barley, grapes, and mustard. The main kharif crops are rice, maize, cotton, groundnuts, bajra (pearl millet), and sugarcane. The Punjab gained importance for its wheat production which increased by more than 2½ times: from 1,900,000 tons in 1965 – 66 to 5,300,000 tons in 1975 – 76. Average wheat yields have gone up from 1.2 to 2.3 t/ha over the same period.

Rice yields in the Punjab are among the highest in India. Rice now seems to be the most profitable kharif crop. The traditional rice varieties such as Jhona 20, Jhona 277, Jhona 349, Palman 246, Basmati 217, and Basmati 370 are weak strawed and tall (150 – 200 cm). They lodge badly when fertilized, so their yield is stabilized at around 1 t/ha. Rice cultivation was previously confined to fields where no other kharif crop could be grown – fields that were waterlogged or affected by salinity or alkalinity. After the introduction of varieties of the semidwarf plant type that are responsive to high fertilization – such as Taichung Native 1 in 1965, IR8 in 1968, Jaya

IRRI can provide scientists with seeds and a description of 110 elite rice lines that have been selected for disease and insect resistance. A major aim of IRRI's GEU program is to incorporate resistance into improved germ plasm. Rizal Herrera, senior research assistant, plant breeding, makes cross.

Changes in rice area, production, and yield after the introduction of varieties of the new plant type. Punjab Agricultural University Rice Research Station, Kapurthala, Punjab, India.

Year	Area planted to rice (1000 ha)	Area planted to semidwarf varieties		Production of milled rice (1000 t)	Yield (t/ha)
		(1000 ha)	(%)		
1950	120	-	-	107	0.79
1955	149	-	-	107	0.72
1960	227	-	-	220	1.1
1965	292	-	-	292	1.0
1966	285	4	1	338	1.2
1967	314	17	5	415	1.3
1968	345	27	8	470	1.4
1969	350	72	20	535	1.5
1970	390	143	38	688	1.8
1971	450	311	73	920	2.0
1972	476	378	79	955	2.0
1973	498	450	84	1140	2.1
1974	570	500	88	1181	2.1
1975	566	500	91	1445	2.6

in 1969, and Palman 579 (IR579-48-1-2) in 1971—the rice crop in the state changed progressively (see table). The area under high-yielding varieties (HYV) increased from 1 percent in 1966 to more than 90 percent in 1975. Correspondingly, rice yield increased from 1.2 to 2.6 t/ha. Total area in rice also increased from 285,000 to 566,000 ha and rice is now being grown on soils where other kharif crops were previously grown. All these factors—particularly the area under HYV—are

responsible for an increase in rice production in the state from 292,000 tons in 1965 to 1,445,000 tons in 1975—about a fivefold increase. Because the majority of the Punjab population do not consume rice, most of the state's production is saved for the Central Rice Pool. In 1975, the Punjab made the highest contribution of any state, 1,100,000 tons of rice, which made up more than 35 percent of the pool.

A new rice variety, Kranti, bred by Jawaharlal Nehru Agricultural University Research Station, Raipur

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A new rice variety, Kranti (sel. no. R 2022), has been developed by the Central Rice Research Station, Raipur,

India, working under Jawaharlal Nehru Agricultural University, Madhya Pradesh. It derives from the cross C-116/IR8. C-116 is a variety bred from a cross between two local varieties, Bhondu and Parewa. Kranti is slightly taller than Jaya (105 vs. 95 cm) so it does better under rainfed conditions than other semidwarfs. Under irrigated conditions

Mean paddy yield of Kranti (R 2022) in several villages. Rice Research Station, Raipur, India.

Variety	Paddy yield (kg/ha)			
	1974		1975	
	Irrigated	Nonirrigated	Irrigated	Nonirrigated
Kranti (R 2022)	4813	1739	6812	4537
Ratna	3890	1499	-	-
Anupama	-	-	5689	3204
C.D. 5%	607	-	428	399

it has also yielded higher than Ratna or Jaya. Kranti matures in 120 days when planted in kharif (June-October) so it fits well into double and multiple cropping patterns.

Its grain is short and bold with shiny strawcolored husk. Its cooking quality is good. Kranti has field resistance to bacterial blight, blast, and false smut.

The RD series of rice varieties developed in Thailand from 1969 to 1975

Rice Division, Department of Agriculture, Ministry of Agriculture and Cooperatives, Thailand

The release of the RD (Rice Division) series of varieties began in 1969 with RD1, RD2, and RD3 and has now progressed to RD9. Glutinous varieties are denoted by even numbers. So far, all releases are essentially insensitive to photoperiod, fall into the general classification of high-yielding varieties, and conform to the Thai grain standards for class 1 milled grain.

The most widely grown new variety is RD1 (LT/IR8). More than 70 percent of the dry-season planting in irrigated areas is estimated to be devoted to it. In recent years, however, its spread has been slowed by bacterial blight and, recently, by brown planthoppers in some fields.

RD2 (TN1/Gam Pai 15) was intended for the areas of north and northeast Thailand where consumers prefer glutinous rice. But it has not been popular among farmers in the northeast, probably because it is short and lacks photoperiod sensitivity. Susceptibility to bacterial blight and to gall midge may also limit its use.

RD3 (LT/IR8) was intended for areas where farmers apply only minimal inputs of fertilizer and other management practices. Data collected before its release suggest that it competes better with weeds and produces higher yields than RD1 at low fertilizer levels. But RD3 has not found favor with most farmers, probably because of its extreme susceptibility to bacterial blight, and long flag leaves that prevent easy visibility of panicles.